

Spectroscopic characterization, biological activities and theoretical computation of manganese(II) and copper(II) complexes of sulfamethoxazolyl-azo-acetylacetone

Dipankar Das^{a†}, Ipsita De^a, Nilima Sahu^a, Suman Roy^a, Nayim Sepay^a, Paramita Dutta^a, Suvroma Gupta^b and Chittaranjan Sinha^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : c_r_sinha@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Biotechnology, Haldia Institute of Technology, Haldia, Purba Medinipur-721 657, West Bengal, India

Manuscript received 20 January 2017, accepted 07 February 2017

Abstract : [4-(Z)-((2-Hydroxy-4-oxopent-2-en-3-yl)diazenyl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide] (sulfamethoxazolyl-azo-acetylacetone, HL) serves as monoanionic N,O chelator and has been used to synthesize manganese(II), [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (1) and copper(II), [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (2) complexes. Different physicochemical techniques (FT-IR, UV-Vis, Mass, SEM-EDX, thermal, bulk magnetic moment, EPR) have been employed to establish the structure and electronic configuration of the complexes. The interaction of CT-DNA with [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (K_b^{Mn} , $1.26 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}$) is stronger than [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (K_b^{Cu} , $6.12 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$) while HL shows least interaction (K_b^{HL} , $6.09 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$). Antimicrobial activity of them have also been examined against *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633; IC₅₀ 77.25 µg/ml (HL), 84.01 µg/ml (1) and 81.5 µg/ml (2)) and *E. coli* (ATCC 8739; IC₅₀ 63.72 µg/ml (HL), 84.01 µg/ml (1) and 85.19 µg/ml (2)). *In silico* test is used to predict the most favored binding pose of the complexes with the active site residues of DHPS (dihydropteroate synthetase) protein of *E. coli*. [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (2) binds more efficiently [ΔG^\ddagger , -2.59 kcal/mol] than [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (1) [ΔG^\ddagger , -1.44 kcal/mol]. DNA docking (1BNA) also shows the binding with the complex 2 (ΔG^\ddagger , -2.87 kcal/mol) is stronger than that of complex, 1 [ΔG^\ddagger , -2.65 kcal/mol].

Keywords : Sulfamethoxazole-azo-acetylacetone, Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, DNA interaction, antibacterial properties, molecular docking.

Introduction

Sulfamethoxazole (SMX) is a useful drug in the treatment of different microbial infections¹⁻⁸. However, long use of SMX induces allergic reactions to skin, stomach, lungs, abdomen, kidney, liver, blood etc.⁹⁻¹³ and hepatotoxicity, lymphadenopathy and hematological disorders¹⁴ which may be due to generation of oxidative metabolites SMX-hydroxylamine (SMX-NHOH) and SMX-nitroso (SMX-NO)¹⁵. The sulfonamide derivatives and their metal complexes^{16,17} are in clinical trials to resolve these issues and to improve drug action. Azo dyes of sulfa drugs are well known for their antiseptic activity¹⁸. A large number of metal sulphonamide complexes are found to be

more potent than the parent drugs¹⁹. Moreover, azo compounds were reported to show antibacterial²⁰, antifungal²¹, antiviral²² and anti-inflammatory²³ activities. In this paper, we have used 4-(Z)-((2-hydroxy-4-oxopent-2-en-3-yl)diazenyl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (HL)²⁴ to synthesize [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (1) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (2) complexes which have been characterised by spectroscopic, thermal, magnetic and electrochemical data. The electronic configuration, spectral and redox properties have been explained by the DFT and TD-DFT computation of optimized structures. The interaction of the complexes with CT-DNA has been studied by spectrophotometric method. Antimicrobial activities

[†]Present address : Greater Kolkata College of Engineering and Management, Ramnagar-II, Piyali Town, Baruipur, 24-Parganas(S)-743 387, West Bengal, India.

have also been explored with *E. coli* (Gram-negative) and *B. subtilis* (Gram-positive) bacteria. To account the drug activity and toxicity the drug-protein interaction of the products has been carried out by molecular docking studies with DHPS protein of *E. coli* at best pose case of the complexes²⁴⁻²⁶. The DNA (1BNA) interaction of the complexes has also been ascertained by molecular docking studies and Cu^{II}-complex shows better activity than Mn^{II} complex.

Experimental

Materials :

Sulfamethoxazole (SMX) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used without further purification. Acetylacetone and M(OAc)₂.xH₂O (M = Mn and x = 4; M = Cu and x = 1) were purchased from Merck, India. [4-(Z)-((2-Hydroxy-4-oxopent-2-en-3-yl)diazenyl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide] (sulfamethoxazolyl-azo-acetylacetone, HL) was prepared following literature report²⁴. Acetonitrile used for electrochemical studies was dried with CaH₂ and distilled prior to use. Calf thymus DNA was bought from Sisco Research Laboratories, India, and dissolved in phosphate buffer (pH ~7.4) containing 120 mM NaCl (AR grade, Merck, Germany). The concentration of calf thymus DNA in terms of nucleotide was determined by taking ε₂₆₀ = 6600 M⁻¹ dm³ cm⁻¹²⁷. NaCl (0.500 M dm⁻³) (AR grade, Merck, Germany) was used to maintain ionic strength.

Physical measurements :

The elemental analyses were performed on Perkin-Elmer model 2400 CHN/S elemental analyzers. Infrared spectra were obtained using Perkin-Elmer RX-1 FTIR spectrophotometer (KBr disk, 4000–400 cm⁻¹). The UV-Vis spectral data were recorded using Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectral data were assembled in suitable solvent using AC Bruker 300, 500 MHz FT NMR spectrometers. The electrochemical studies were accomplished with use of computer controlled CH Instruments Electrochemical Workstation. All experiments were compassed at 298 K under N₂ atmosphere with a three electrodes system, platinum and glassy carbon (GC) as working electrode in MeCN. All potentials are referred to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and are uncorrected for the junction contributions with n-tetra-butyl ammonium perchlorate, [nBu₄N][ClO₄] (TBAP), as supporting electrolyte. The

thermal analysis (TGA/DTG) was carried out under N₂ atmosphere with a heating rate of 12 °C/min (150 ml/min) using Pyris Diamond TG/DTA analyzer made of Perkin-Elmer (Singapore) and platinum crucible used with α-Al₂O₃ powder as reference. The SEM-EDX analyses were executed with the help of a computer controlled field emission SEM (JEOL, JSM-6330F, JEOL Ltd.) equipped with EDX detection system by the dint of Oxford Instrument.

Syntheses of the complexes :

To methanol solution (10 ml) of M(OAc)₂.xH₂O (Mn(OAc)₂.4H₂O : 30 mg, 0.122 mmol or Cu(OAc)₂.H₂O : 30 mg, 0.150 mmol) in a round bottom flask, two equivalent of HL (100 mg, 0.273 mmol) in MeOH (10 ml) and 0.1 ml of Et₃N was added and stirred (Scheme 1). The solution was stirred for 4 h followed by 6 h refluxing and then cooled to room temperature, settled and filtered. Residue was washed with MeOH-water (1 : 1, v/v). Green manganese and ash colored copper complexes were recrystallized from DMF-methanol (1 : 4, v/v) mixture.

Microanalytical data for [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) : Anal. Calcd. for MnC₃₀H₃₈N₈O₁₄S₂ (Mol. wt. 853.1) (%) : C, 42.20; H, 4.45; N, 13.16; Found (%) : C, 42.34; H, 4.34; N, 13.06. [M⁺] m/z = 879.37. FT-IR (KBr, ν, cm⁻¹) (N=N), 1403; ν(C=N), 1615; ν(C=O), 1684; ν(O-H), 3431; ν(S-O), 1159.

Microanalytical data for [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) : Anal. Calcd. for CuC₃₀H₃₈N₈O₁₄S₂ (Mol. wt. 861.1) (%) : C, 41.80; H, 4.41; N, 13.00; Found (%) : C, 41.72; H, 4.32; N, 12.95. [M⁺] m/z = 887.75. FT-IR (KBr, ν, cm⁻¹) (N=N), 1402; ν(C=N), 1613; ν(C=O), 1684; ν(O-H), 3452; ν(S-O), 1158²⁸. Spectra of both complexes are given as Supplementary Material (Figs. S1-S5 and Table S1).

Antibacterial studies :

The ligand, HL and the complexes, [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) had been needed to examine their antibacterial activity. The compounds had been dissolved in 100% DMSO and stored at -20 °C. Gram-positive *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633) and Gram-negative *E. coli* (ATCC 8739), inoculated in a freshly prepared autoclaved LB broth from a 24 h old LA slant, and were kept in shaker for overnight. The overnight culture was diluted

Interaction of the complexes with calf thymus DNA :

Preparation of solutions for DNA binding studies :

A stock solution (10 ml) of both $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**) complexes were prepared by dissolving (1.1 mg, 0.0012 mmol of **1** and 1.35 mg, 0.0015 mmol of **2**) in DMSO. These solutions were diluted with tris-HCl buffer for preparation of working cell concentration for the experiment. Absorption spectral titration experiment was performed by keeping constant concentration of the complexes with varying concentration of CT-DNA. To eliminate the absorbance of DNA itself, equal solution of CT-DNA was added either to $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ or $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ solution.

Preparation of calf thymus DNA :

The tris-HCl buffer solution (pH 8.0), used in all the experiments involving CT-DNA, was made by using deionized and sonicated HPLC grade water (Merck). The CT-DNA used in the experiments was sufficiently free from protein. The concentration of DNA was determined with the help of its extinction coefficient ϵ of $6600 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 260 nm^{24} . Stock solution of DNA was always stored at 4°C and used within 4 days.

Absorption spectroscopic studies of the complexes in presence of CT-DNA :

Absorption spectroscopic studies were done on a spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, Lambda-25), using $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (0.104 μM) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (0.251 μM) complexes with increasing concentrations of CT-DNA (0, 0.402, 0.802, 1.20, 1.59 μM) and (0, 0.402, 0.802, 1.20, 1.59, 1.98, 2.37 μM). After each addition, the mixture of DNA and the compounds were incubated at room temperature for 15 min and scanned at 250–600 nm wave length for the above compounds. The self-absorption of DNA was eliminated in each set of experiments. Each sample was scanned for a cycle number of 2, cycle time of 5 s at a scan speed of 100 nm/min. Modified Benesi-Hildebrand²⁴ plot was used for the determination of ground state binding constant between the compounds and CT-DNA. The binding constant K_b was determined by using the relation $A_0/\Delta A = A_0/\Delta A_{\text{max}} + (A_0/\Delta A_{\text{max}}) \times (1/K) \times (1/L_t)$ where $\Delta A = A_0 - A$, ΔA_{max} = maximum change in reduced absorbance, A_0 = maximum absorbance of receptor molecules (without any DNA), A = reduced absorbance of receptor molecules

(in presence of DNA), L_t = DNA concentration.

Computational aspects :

$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**) complexes were used as input functions in the Density functional theory (DFT) calculations and the optimized geometries of **1** and **2** were generated. The calculations have been carried out with the B3LYP-6-31G(d) basis set for C, H, N and Cl and LanL2DZ^{30,31} is used for Mn, Cu and S using the Gaussian 09 program. The entire calculations including graphical representations of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) data in the checkpoint files were performed³² with the aid of the Gauss View visualization program^{33,34}. The vibrational frequency calculations were accomplished to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima and there are only positive eigen values. Vertical electronic excitations based on B3LYP optimized geometries were computed for HL. The time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) formalism^{35–37} in dichloromethane using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)^{38–40} was used for the complexes. Gauss Sum was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital⁴¹.

Results and discussion

The synthesis and formulation :

4-(Z)-((2-Hydroxy-4-oxopent-2-en-3-yl)diazonyl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)benzene sulfonamide (HL) has been synthesized following published procedure²⁴ by diazotization of sulfamethoxazole (SMX) followed by the coupling of diazonium ion ($\text{SMX-N}=\text{N}^+$) with acetylacetone (Hacac) in basic medium. Nickel(II) complex has been reported in literature²⁴ and becomes the guideline to present work. $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**) complexes have been isolated and characterized by spectroscopic data (FT-IR, Figs. S1, S2; UV-Vis, Figs. S3, S4; Mass, Figs. S5, S6; Supplementary Materials). The electronic spectra of the complexes are recorded in DMF and show intense band at 372 and 364 nm respectively and have been assigned to π - π^* transitions. The d-d band in DMF solution of the complexes appears at 500 nm (**1**) and 550 nm (**2**), respectively (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S4). The bond distance between Cu(1)-O(1) and Cu(1)-N(1) are 2.022 Å and 2.013 Å⁴² and of

Mn(1)-O(1), Mn(1)-N(1) are 2.175 Å and 2.221 Å respectively shown in Table 1. The complexes start dehydration at 82 °C (Obsd. = 8.40%, Calcd. = 8.43% for **1** and Obsd. = 8.32%, Calcd. = 8.34% for **2**)²⁴ and finally decomposition starts at 250 °C and has been completed at 400 °C (Supplementary Material, Figs. S7-S10). The cyclic voltammogram of [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] complexes in acetonitrile show irreversible azo reduction at -1.0 V (ΔE , 200 mV) (Supplementary Material, Fig. S11a,b).

The magnetic moment is recorded at 305 K and μ_{eff} are 4.87 BM for **1** and 1.50 BM for **2** respectively. These data support d⁵ (high spin) of [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and d⁹ electronic configuration of [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) of the com-

axial spectra with g_{\parallel} 2.24. The results are in general agreement with the electronic spectra, which also suggest the existence of octahedral. From the observed g -tensor values of the Cu^{II} complexes it is clear that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ agrees with the ground state configuration of $d_{x^2-y^2}$ giving ²B_{1g} as the ground state.

Powder X-ray diffraction and SEM and EDX studies :

The powder X-ray diffraction pattern for [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complexes (Supplementary Material, Fig. S14a,b) and their SEM image show that the complex **1** is crystalline (Supplementary Material, Fig. S15) while complex **2** is amorphous (Supplementary Material, Fig. S16). The chemical analy-

Table 1. Theoretical bond length (Å) and bond angle (°) of [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄]

Bond length (Å)				Bond angle (°)	
[Mn(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (1)		[Cu(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (2)		[Mn(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] and [Cu(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	
Length type	Theoretical	Length type	Theoretical	Angle type	Bond angle (°) Theoretical
N(3)-N(4)	1.288	N(3)-N(4)	1.288	N(3)-N(4)-C(11)	126.45
Mn(1)-N(1)	2.221	Cu(1)-N(1)	2.013	N(4)-N(3)-C(8)	121.91
Mn(1)-O(7)	2.175	Cu(1)-O(7)	2.022	O(3)-S(1)-O(2)	121.15
Mn(1)-O(6)	2.248	Cu(1)-O(6)	2.398	O(3)-S(1)-N(2)	112.97
N(1)-C(3)	1.363	N(1)-C(3)	1.363	O(2)-S(1)-N(2)	105.35
N(2)-C(3)	1.371	N(2)-C(3)	1.371	O(3)-S(1)-C(5)	106.03
S(1)-O(3)	1.463	S(1)-O(3)	1.463	O(2)-S(1)-C(5)	106.12
S(1)-O(2)	1.467	S(1)-O(2)	1.467		
S(1)-N(2)	1.572	S(1)-N(2)	1.572		
O(1)-C(1)	1.395	O(1)-C(1)	1.395		
O(1)-N(1)	1.458	O(1)-N(1)	1.458		

plexes. The EPR spectra at solid state shows existence of active paramagnetic electron to Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} in **1** and **2**, respectively. The EPR spectra of [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (Supplementary Material, Fig. S12a,b) in MeCN at 77 K displays $g \approx 2.07$, $m_s = +1/2$ to $-1/2$ fine structure transition splits into six hyperfine lines as expected for ⁵⁵Mn^{II} ($I = 5/2$) along with superfine splitting. Each hyperfine shows doublet splitting at 77 K which suggests interaction of ligand-N with Mn^{II}. Solid state EPR spectra of [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) (Supplementary Material, Fig. S13c,d) at room temperature (298 K) are weakly resolved. The resolution is better at 77 K in MeCN solution. The complexes show usual four line (⁶³Cu, $I = 3/2$) EPR spectra and are anisotropic at higher magnetic field. They exhibit

ses by EDX show a homogenous distribution between metal ions and chelating agent which determines the elemental composition. The analyses of [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] reveals that K_{α} peak of Mn appears at 5.8 KeV, 6.5 KeV and 0.9 KeV respectively whereas oxygen K_{α} peak comes at 0.50 KeV⁴³, carbon and nitrogen peaks are observed at 0.10 KeV and 0.20 KeV while sulphur shows K_{α} peak at 2.30 KeV⁴³. The analyses of [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] reveals that O, C and N appear at K_{α} peak 0.51 KeV, 0.10 KeV and 0.20 KeV respectively, but sulphur shows K_{α} peak at 2.40 KeV along with Cu K_{α} peak at 8.0 KeV, 9.0 KeV and 0.80 KeV. Elemental quantitative analyses yield the weight and atomic percentages of the elements present in Supplementary Material, Table S2.

Antibacterial potential of HL, [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄]:

The antibacterial activity of HL, [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) have been examined against *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633) and *E. coli* (ATCC 8739). The compounds exhibited inhibition of bacterial growth after 18–20 h of compound administration. The IC₅₀ (the concentration of test compound required to inhibit the growth of bacteria by 50%) for HL, **1** and **2** have been determined and presented in Figs. 1, 2 and result has been given in Table 2. The IC₅₀ values are 63.72 µg/ml (HL), 84.01 µg/ml (**1**) and 85.19 µg/ml (**2**) for Gram-negative *E. coli* (ATCC 8739) and 77.25 µg/ml (HL), 84.01 µg/ml (**1**) and 81.5 µg/ml (**2**) for Gram-positive *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633). The concentration dependant decrease in the growth of both Gram-positive *B. subtilis* and Gram-negative *E. coli* bacteria is observed. Metal ions are able to produce antibacterial effect due to “oligodynamic action” as manifested from their use in the killing of micro-organism^{44,45}. SMX is a useful drug to biomedical treatment due to its cost efficiency and shows IC₅₀ of SMX for *E. coli*, 300 µg/ml and for *B. subtilis*, 176 µg/ml that is higher than HL, **1** and **2**. However its use has been restricted due to toxicity. The functionalization of SMX and its metallo-organic derivatives may be useful in the future drug design and medical treatment.

Interaction of the complexes with CT-DNA : Absorption spectroscopic studies :

The interaction of both [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complexes with CT-DNA have been investigated by spectrophotometric method. Addition of increasing amounts of CT-DNA resulted in an increase in absorbency without any shift in the absorption maxima (372 nm for **1** and 364 nm for **2** complexes) in the UV spectra. In general, an intercalative interaction of the aromatic chromophore and the base pairs of DNA helix are reflected by hyperchromism and red shift of charge transfer band⁴⁶. The spectral changes of both [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complexes (Figs. 3, 4) observed in the presence of CT-DNA which can be illustrated in terms of groove binding^{47,48}. It is reported that aromatic ring of the molecule closely matches with the helical turn of the CT-DNA groove and the aromatic rings of ligand interacts with DNA in Tris-HCl buffer through

Fig. 1. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) of HL, [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) in the presence of *E. coli* (ATCC 8739).

Fig. 2. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) of HL, [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) in the presence of *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633).

Table 2. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) value of HL, [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) in the presence of *E. coli* (ATCC 8739) and *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633)

Comps.	(IC ₅₀) value in the presence of <i>E. coli</i> (ATCC 8739) (µg/ml)	(IC ₅₀) value in the presence of <i>B. subtilis</i> (ATCC 6633) (µg/ml)
SMX	300	176
HL	63.72	77.25
[Mn(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (1)	84.01	84.01
[Cu(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (2)	85.19	81.50

the formation of the van der Waal’s contacts or hydrogen bonds in DNA grooves. At the absorption maximum, we have calculated the binding constant for [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**), 1.26 × 10⁶ M⁻¹ and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**), 6.12 × 10⁵ M⁻¹ with DNA by using modified Benesi-Hildebrand (BH)

Fig. 3. Absorption spectroscopic study of $0.1024 \mu\text{M}$ $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) with increasing concentrations of CT-DNA (0, 0.402, 0.802, 1.20, 1.59 μM) respectively (1 \rightarrow 5).

Fig. 4. Absorption spectroscopic study of $0.2496 \mu\text{M}$ $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**) with increasing concentrations of CT-DNA (0, 0.402, 0.802, 1.20, 1.59, 1.98, 2.37 μM) respectively (1 \rightarrow 7).

plot (Supplementary Material, Fig. S17a,b). The binding constant (K_b) of HL is $6.09 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ²⁴. The free energy ΔG^\ddagger are -8.37 kcal for $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) and -7.95 kcal for $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**). A negative value of free energy is indicative of the spontaneity of the complex-DNA binding and implies better interaction with metal complexes compared to free ligand. The results support the interaction of the complexes with DNA through groove binding of the aromatic chromospheres and the base pairs of DNA.

Molecular docking studies of ligand with DHPS in presence of E. coli :

Docking studies of molecules with DHPS protein structure (obtained from Protein Data Bank) are useful to predict the most probable mode of interaction for the efficiency of them to function as drugs. The docking result reveals important information regarding interaction mode

of ligand with enzyme inside binding pockets. Sulfamethoxazole bound crystallographic structure of dihydropteroate synthase has been downloaded from RCSB-PDB (Protein Data Bank, <http://www.rcsb.org/pdb/home/home.do>) with PDB id 3TZF which is resolved at 2.10 \AA using X-ray diffraction. The *in silico* test of HL with DHPS protein from *E. coli* assigns two types of hydrogen bonds in the best pose structure in the protein pocket (2.25 , 2.39 and 2.94 \AA with Arg63; 2.03 , 2.76 and 2.05 \AA with Arg235) while SMX shows hydrogen bond with Arg63 2.345 \AA only ²⁴. At present two complexes, **1** and **2**, large number of hydrogen bonds and establish their better drug potency than organic precursor. Inside the binding sphere of DHPS (PDB id 1AJ0, *E. coli*), there are thirteen amino acid residues such as Arg267, Ala50, Val263, Asn49, Ala52, Ile48, Thr53, Asn45, Arg88, Gln87, Phe89, Glu90, Val91 and there are thirteen amino acid residues (PDB id 2VEG, *B. subtilis*) such as Asn252, Val251, Glu250, Arg236, Phe151, Glu245, Pro253, Arg262, Arg238, Ile241, Gly205, Lys237, Ile150 that binds with $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) complex by H-bonds (Supplementary Material, Figs. S18-S19). Similarly inside the binding sphere of DHPS (PDB id 1AJ0, *E. coli*), there are fifteen amino acid residues such as Ser233, Ser237, Glu234, Arg235, Leu236, Asn49, Ala50, Leu46, Glu261, Lys260, His257, Met47, Val259, Arg220, Asp258 and there are twelve amino acid residues (PDB id 2VEG, *B. subtilis*) such as His7, Asn6, Ala8, Pro195, Gly227, Lys226, Glu196, Tyr228, Gln225, Pro229, Glu279, Leu185 that binds with $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**) complex by H-bonds (Supplementary Material, Figs. S20-S21). Binding energy in the protein pockets of DHPS (*E. coli*) reveal that $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**) binds more efficiently [ΔG^\ddagger (Cu, *E. coli*), -2.59 kcal/mol] than $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) [ΔG^\ddagger (Mn, *E. coli*), -1.44 kcal/mol] in the DHPS cavity of 1AJ0 protein; similarly DHPS (*B. subtilis*) binds efficiently with Cu^{II} complex (**2**) [ΔG^\ddagger (Cu, *B. subtilis*), -2.87 kcal/mol] than Mn^{II} complex (**1**) [ΔG^\ddagger (Mn, *B. subtilis*), -2.65 kcal/mol] (Table 3).

Interaction analysis suggests that when $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) complex binds with DHPS of 1AJ0, 2VEG, oxygen atom of $-\text{SO}_2$, acetylacetonate, oxazolyl moiety azo-N atoms, form total six recognizable H-bonds with protein residue such as Arg88 N-H \cdots O-C is 2.26 \AA , Arg267 N-H \cdots O-C is 2.24 \AA , Glu90 (HO-)CO \cdots H-O-Mn is 3.49 \AA

for 1AJ0 and Arg238 N-H---O-(SO₂⁻) is 2.31 Å, Arg236 N-H---O-(SO₂⁻) is 2.49 Å, Lys237 N-H---O-(SO₂⁻) is 2.62 Å (Figs. 5, 6) and whereas [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complex binds with DHPS of 1AJ0, oxygen atom of -SO₂, acetylacetonate, oxazolyl moiety azo-N atoms, form total five recognizable H-bonds with protein residue such as Asn49 (-CO)N-H---O-C is 2.36 Å, Val259 (-CO)N-H---O-(SO₂⁻) is 2.37 Å, Lys260 (-CO)N-H---O-(SO₂⁻) is 2.52 Å, Asp258 (HO-)CO---H-O-Mn is 1.91 Å, Asp258 (HO) CO---H-N(SO₂⁻) is 2.78 Å for 1AJ0 (Supplementary Material, Figs. S22-S23). Relevant different type of H-bonds and π---π interactions of DHPS of 1AJ0, 2VEG with [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complexes are shown in Supplementary Material (Table S3).

Interaction analysis also suggests that when [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) complex binds with DNA (PDB id 1BNA), oxygen atom of -SO₂, acetylacetonate, oxazolyl moiety azo-N atoms, form total three recognizable H-bonds with protein residue such as Chain B G14 N-H---O-(SO₂⁻) is 2.52 Å, Chain B G14(sugar) O---H-O-(H₂O-Mn) is 2.27 Å, Chain B G14(sugar) O---H-O-(H₂O-Mn) is 2.77 Å (Supplementary Material, Fig. S24) and whereas [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complex binds with DNA (PDB id 1BNA), oxygen atom of -SO₂, acetylacetonate, oxazolyl moiety azo-N atoms form, total five recognizable H-bonds with protein residue such as Chain B G22 (PO₃⁻)O---H-N(SO₂⁻) is 3.07 Å, Chain B G22 (PO₃⁻)O---H-O-(H₂O-Cu) is 3.03 Å, Chain B G22 (PO₃⁻)O---H-O-(H₂O-Cu) is 3.09 Å, Chain A A5 N-H---O-(SO₂⁻) is 2.64 Å, Chain A T7 (PO₃⁻)O---H-O-(H₂O-Cu) is 2.28 Å (Supplementary Material, Fig. S25). The docking of these two complexes (**1** and **2**) with DNA duplex of the sequence

(CGCGAATTCGCG)₂ dodecamer (PDB id 1BNA) have been used to predict the mode of binding and the binding strength⁴⁹. It has been observed that binding of all the drug molecules was stabilized by one or more H-bonds and stacking interaction with DNA bases. Relevant different type of H bonds and π---π interactions of DNA (PDB id 1BNA) with [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complexes are shown in Supplementary Material (Table S4). Surface docking pose of 1AJ0 and DNA (1BNA) for [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complexes are shown in Supplementary Material, Figs. S26-S28. Docking pose of DHPS of 1AJ0, *B. subtilis* of 2VEG, surface docking pose of 2VEG and hydrophobicity for [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complexes are shown in Supplementary Material, Figs. S29-S34.

DFT computation :

The structural pattern has been evaluated from the bond parameters calculated by the DFT optimized structures of [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) (Table 1). DFT and TD-DFT computations of the complexes are carried out to determine the composition and energy of the molecular levels (Supplementary Materials, Tables S5-S12). To simplify analysis of DFT computation result the structure of HL has been divided into benzene sulfonamide (BSN), methyloxazolyl (MOX) and azo-acetylacetonate (AAA) (Fig. 7). The composition of MOs and proposed electronic transitions in acetonitrile (CH₃CN) solution of [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (Supplementary Material, Tables S8-S12) suggest that azo function (AAA) is electron acceptor while methyloxazolyl (MOX) and

Table 3. Relevant different types of energy in protein (DHPS) – [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**1**), [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (**2**) complexes and DNA (1BNA) – [Mn(L)₂(H₂O)₄], [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] complexes

Compds.	PDB id of protein/DNA	Change of free energy (ΔG) (kcal/mol)	Complex efficiency (a.u.)	Inter-molecular energy (kcal/mol)	Vdw H-bonded energy (kcal/mol)	Electrostatic energy (kcal/mol)	Total internal energy (kcal/mol)	Torsional energy (kcal/mol)	Unbound energy (kcal/mol)	Inhibition constant
[Mn(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (1)	1AJ0	-1.44	-0.33	-7.4	-7.21	-0.19	-8.03	5.97	-8.03	88.71
	2VEG	-2.22	-0.04	-8.18	-7.98	-0.2	-8.79	5.97	-8.79	23.78
	DNA (1BNA)	-2.65	-0.05	-8.62	-8.4	-0.22	-10.24	5.97	-10.24	11.35
[Cu(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (2)	1AJ0	-2.59	-0.05	-8.86	-9.25	0.4	-8.48	5.97	-8.48	7.61
	2VEG	-1.75	-0.03	-7.72	-7.81	0.09	-11.6	5.97	-11.31	51.94
	DNA (1BNA)	-2.87	-0.05	-8.83	-9.05	0.22	-8.98	5.97	-8.98	7.94

Fig. 5. Docking pose for hydrogen bonding interaction of 1AJ0 with $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (1) complex (2D).

Fig. 6. Docking pose for hydrogen bonding interaction of 2VEG with $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (1) complex (2D).

benzene sulfonamide (BSN) either separately or jointly donate electrons.

In case of selected α molecular orbital of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, the HOMO is constituted of 35% BSN, 22% MOX, 30% AAA; the LUMO has 28% contribution from BSN and 33% AAA (Supplementary material, Fig. S35). So, the HOMO \rightarrow LUMO may be assigned to intra-molecular charge transfer from BSN \rightarrow AAA. In β mo-

lecular orbitals of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, the HOMO is constituted of 34% BSN, 10% MOX, 56% AAA; the LUMO has 21% contribution from BSN, and 79% AAA (Supplementary material, Fig. S36). So, the HOMO to LUMO transition may be assigned to intra-molecular charge transfer from BSN \rightarrow AAA, MOX \rightarrow AAA.

In case of selected α molecular orbital of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, the HOMO is constituted of 29% BSN,

Fig. 7. Contour plots of some selected molecular orbitals and spin density of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**) complexes.

05% MOX, 66% AAA; the LUMO has 21% contribution from BSN, and 79% AAA (Supplementary material, Fig. S37). So, the HOMO→LUMO may be assigned to intra-molecular charge transfer from BSN→AAA. In β molecular orbitals of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, the HOMO is constituted of 52% BSN, 41% MOX, 04% AAA; the LUMO

has 53% contribution from BSN, and 06% AAA (Supplementary material, Fig. S38). So, the HOMO to LUMO transition may be assigned to intra-molecular charge transfer from BSN→AAA, MOX→AAA.

In $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, the electronic transitions at 372 nm is due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. In CH_3CN the calculated

transition appears at 377.85 nm (f , 0.0336) for α molecular orbital of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$. The observed transitions are close to the calculated one in α molecular orbital of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$. In CH_3CN the calculated transition appears at 387.99 nm (f , 0.0298) for β molecular orbital of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$. In $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, the electronic transitions at 364 nm is due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. In CH_3CN the calculated transition appears at 373.20 nm (f , 0.0561) for α molecular orbital of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$. The observed transitions are close to the calculated one in α molecular orbital of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$. In CH_3CN the calculated transition appears at 374.22 nm (f , 0.1187) for β molecular orbital of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$.

Conclusion

Sulfamethoxazolyl-azo-acetylacetone (HL) and $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**1**) and copper(II), $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ (**2**) complexes have been spectroscopically characterized. The antibacterial study shows that IC_{50} value (*E. coli* : SMX, 85.19 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; HL, 63.72 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; **1**, 84.01 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; **2**, 85.19 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of *B. subtilis* : SMX, 176 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; HL, 77.25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; **1**, 84.01 $\mu\text{g/ml}$; **2**, 81.50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of them is less than the parent SMX molecule, so synthesized molecule are more biologically active than SMX. In terms of DNA interaction it also proved that K_b value of metal complexes is higher than ligand and SMX due to high polarity of metal complexes.

Abbreviations

SMX	Sulfamethoxazole
CT-DNA	Calf thymus DNA
MIC	Minimum inhibitory concentration
Ligand (HL)	Sulfamethoxazole-azo-acetylacetone
EDX	Energy dispersive X-ray spectrum

Supplementary materials

Physicochemical data of the complexes are given in as follows : FT-IR, Figs. S1, S2; UV-Vis, Figs. S3, S4; Mass, Figs. S5, S6; Thermal, Figs. S7-S10; cyclic voltammogram, Fig. S11a,b; EPR, Figs. S12a,b, S13c,d; Powder-XRD, Figs. S14a,b; SEM-EDX, Figs. S15-S16; Benesi-Hildebrand plot for CT-DNA, Fig. S17a,b; Docking figures, Figs. S18-S34; α -FMOs of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ **1**, Fig. S35; β -FMOs of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, Fig. S36; α -FMOs of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ **2**, Fig. S37; β -FMOs of

$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, Fig. S38; UV, IR data, Table S1; SEM-EDX analyses of the complexes, Table S2; Docking information of the complexes with DHPS H-bonded data, Table S3; Docking of the complexes with DNA H-bonded data, Table S4; composition and energy of the molecular levels, Tables S5-S8; Electronic transitions, Tables S9-S12.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from West Bengal DST, Kolkata (No. 228/1(10)/(Sanc.)/ST/P/S&T/9G-16/2012) and UGC (F. 31-123/2005) (SR) are thankfully acknowledged.

References

1. J.-Y. Winum, A. Maresca, F. Carta, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 8177.
2. Z. H. Chohan, M. H. Youssoufi, A. Jarrahpour and T. Benhadda, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 1189.
3. R.-J. Lu, J. A. Tucker, T. Zinevitch, O. Kirichenko, V. Konoplev, S. Kuznetsova, S. Sviridov, J. Pickens, S. Tandel, E. Brahmachary, Y. Yang, J. Wang, S. Freely, S. Fisher, A. Sullivan, J. Hou, S. Stanfield-Oakley, M. Greenberg, D. Bolognesi, B. Bray, B. Koszalka, P. Jeffs, A. Khasanov, Y.-A. Ma, C. Jeffries, C. Liu, T. Proskurina, T. Zhu, A. Chucholowski, R. Li and C. Sexton, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **50**, 6535.
4. G. Xia, L. Liu, M. Xue, H. Liu, J. Yu, P. Li, Q. Chen, B. Xiong, X. Liu and J. Shen, *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.*, 2012, **358**, 46.
5. K. G. Andanappa, S. M. Chanabasappa, N. Sudarshan and R. Anandkumar, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **35**, 853.
6. X. L. Wang, K. Wan and C. H. Zhou, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 4631.
7. M. E. Epstein, M. Amodio-Groton and N. S. Sadick, *J. Am. Acad. Dermatol.*, 1997, **37**, 365.
8. J. D. Smilack, *Mayo Clin. Proc.*, 1999, **74**, 730.
9. G. C. Slatore and A. S. Tilles, *Immunol. Allergy Clin. North Am.*, 2004, **24**, 477.
10. G. Choquet-Kastylevsky, T. Vial and J. Descotes, *Curr. Allergy Asthma Rep.*, 2002, **2**, 16.
11. A. Carr, A. S. Gross, J. M. Hoskins, R. Penny and A. D. Cooper, *Aids.*, 1994, **8**, 333.
12. M. F. Gordin, L. G. Simon, B. C. Wofsy and J. Mills, *Ann. Intern. Med.*, 1984, **100**, 495.
13. L. S. Walmsley, S. Khorasheh, J. Singer and O. Djurdjev, *J. Acquir. Immunogenic. Syndr Human Retroviral*, 1998, **19**, 498.
14. S. Mukesh and E. C. Alastair, *Chemico-Biological Interactions*, 2002, **142**, 155.

15. D. J. Naisbitt, J. Farrell, F. S. Gordon, L. J. Maggs, C. Burkhardt, J. W. Pichler, M. Pirmohamed and K. B. Park, *Mol. Pharmaco.*, 2002, **62**, 628.
16. M. S. Iqbal, A. H. Khan, B. A. Loothar and I. H. Bukhari, *Med. Chem. Res.*, 2009, **18**, 31.
17. Z. H. Chohan and H. A. Shad, *Appl. Organometal. Chem.*, 2011, **25**, 591.
18. K. Lal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17A**, 313.
19. L. Goodman and A. Gilman, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 4th ed., MacMillian, New York, 1970, 1111.
20. P. Pathak, S. V. Jolly and P. K. Sharma, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 2000, **16**, 161.
21. H. Xu and X. Zeng, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2010, **20**, 4193.
22. M. Tonelli, I. Vazzana, B. Tasso, V. Boido, F. Sparatore, M. Fermeiglia, S. M. Paneni, P. Posocco, S. Pricl, P. Colla, C. Ibba, B. Secci, G. Collu and R. Loddo, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **17**, 4425.
23. P. Rani, K. V. Srivastava and A. Kumar, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **39**, 449.
24. D. Das, N. Sahu, S. Mondal, S. Roy, P. Dutta, S. Gupta, T. K. Mondal and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2015, **99**, 77.
25. S. Mondal, S. M. Mandal, T. K. Mondal and C. Sinha, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2015, **150**, 268.
26. D. Das, N. Sahu, S. Roy, P. Dutta, S. Mondal, E.-L. Torres and C. Sinha, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2015, **137**, 560.
27. M. E. Reichmann, S. A. Rice, C. A. Thomas and P. J. Doty, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 3047.
28. A. M. Mansour, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2014, **67**, 2680.
29. J. Kirkpatrick, *Nat. Rev. Drug Disc.*, 2004, **3**, 294.
30. LanL2DZ : P. J. Hay and W. R. J. Wadt, *Chem. Phys.*, 1985, **82**, 299.
31. M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, J. A. Montgomery (Jr.), T. Vreven, K. N. Kudin, J. C. Burant, J. M. Millam, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, M. Cossi, G. Scalmani, N. Rega, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, I. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, M. Klene, X. Li, J. E. Knox, H. P. Hratchian, J. B. Cross, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, P. Y. Ayala, K. Morokuma, V. G. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, V. G. Zakrzewski, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, M. C. Strain, O. Farkas, D. K. Malick, A. D. Rabuck, K. Raghavachari, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, Q. Cui, A. G. Baboul, S. Clifford, J. Cioslowski, B. B. Stefanov, G. Liu, A. Liashenko, P. Piskorz, I. Komaromi, R. L. Martin, D. J. Fox, T. Keith, M. A. Al-Laham, C. Y. Peng, A. Nanayakkara, M. P. Challacombe, M. W. Gill, B. Johnson, W. Chen, M. W. Wong, C. Gonzalez and J. A. Pople, Gaussian 03, Revision B.01, Gaussian, Inc., Pittsburgh PA, 2003.
32. Gaussian Inc., Gaussian03 Program, Gaussian Inc., Wallingford, 2004.
33. Gauss View3.0, Gaussian, Pittsburgh, PA.
34. A. Frisch, A. B. Nielson and A. J. Holder, GAUSSVIEW User Manual, Gaussian Inc., Pittsburgh, PA, 2000.
35. R. Bauernschmitt and R. Ahlrichs, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1996, **256**, 454.
36. R. E. Stratmann, G. E. Scuseria and M. J. Frisch, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **109**, 8218.
37. M. E. Casida, C. Jamorski, K. C. Casida and D. R. Salahub, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **108**, 4439.
38. V. Barone and M. Cossi, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 1998, **102**, 1995.
39. M. Cossi and V. Barone, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2001, **115**, 4708.
40. M. Cossi, N. Rega, G. Scalmani and V. Barone, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2003, **24**, 669.
41. N. M. O'Boyle, A. L. Tenderholt and K. M. Langner, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2008, **29**, 839.
42. S. M. Tailor and U. H. Patel, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2015, **68**, 2192.
43. L. Corbari, M.-A. Cambon-Bonavita, G. J. Long, F. Grandjean, M. Zbinden, F. Gaill and P. Compere, *Biogeosciences*, 2008, **5**, 1295.
44. R. Shrestha, D. R. Joshi, J. Gopali and S. Piya, *Nepal J. Sci. Tech.*, 2009, **10**, 189.
45. P. Kaur and D. Vadehra, *J. Hyg. Epidemiol. Microbiol. Immunol.*, 1988, **32**, 299.
46. A. M. Pyle, J. P. Rehmman, R. Meshoyrer, C. V. Kumar, N. J. Turro and J. K. Barton, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 3051.
47. J. Marmur, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1961, **3**, 208.
48. M. A. Tsiaggali, E. G. Andreadou, A. G. Hatzidimitriou, A. A. Pantazaki and P. Aslanidis, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2013, **121**, 121.
49. W. Hu, S. Deng, J. Huang, Y. Lu, X. Le and W. Zheng, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2013, **127**, 90.